

Copper and Uranyl Chelates of Substituted Succinic and Malonic Acids in Dioxane-Water Mixtures[†]

B. R. ARBAD*

Department of Chemistry, Marathwada University, Aurangabad-431 004

Manuscript received 4 June 1982, revised 6 September 1983, accepted 30 August 1985

Carboxymethylthiosuccinic acid (CMTSA) has three dissociable COOH groups, whose pK values (2.91, 3.91, 5.03) have been determined by various methods of calculations. Copper and uranyl chelates of substituted succinic and malonic acids have been studied by Calvin-Bjerrum potentiometric titration technique at 30° and 0.1 M ionic strength. It was observed that Cu^{II} forms 1:1 and 1:2 chelates with malonic acids and 1:1 chelate with succinic acid in an aqueous medium. All the chelates, except those of mercapto-substituted succinic acids, follow the relationship $\log K = a pK + b$.

THE study of binary complexes of dicarboxylic acids with Cu^{II} and UO_2^{II} has been carried out very extensively because these acids form stable complexes at lower pH . It was observed that Cu^{II} forms 1:1 and 1:2 chelates with malonic acids and 1:1 chelate with succinic acid in aqueous medium. The nature of binding sites of transition metal ions with substituted succinic acids containing mercapto group is not clearly established in many of the earlier studies^{1,2}.

The carboxymethylthiosuccinic acid (CMTSA) molecule has three COOH groups which normally would not show much difference in their pK values. This speculation has been confirmed from the observed pK values of CMTSA by various methods. Accurate determination of pK would, therefore, be a challenge worth undertaking. The present study was undertaken to study exhaustively the complexation equilibria of CMTSA which is a substituted derivative of thiosuccinic acid. As a natural consequence, the simple derivatives of succinic and thiosuccinic acids were also selected for potentiometric study. The purpose of the present study was to obtain more precise information about the behaviour of these ligands in solution and stability constants of their complexes. In particular, it was tried (i) to assign the pK values of substituent groups in succinic and malonic acids, (ii) to establish whether these ligands can form 1:2 chelates in the solvent mixtures with dielectric constant lower than water, (iii) to confirm the exact complexation equilibria of the complexes, (iv) to study the effect of dielectric constant on the stabilities, and (v) to distinguish the effect of substituent groups on the stabilities.

Experimental

Succinic and its chloro, mercapto, dimercapto, amino, hydroxy and carboxymethylthio acids, and

malonic acid and its methyl-substituted derivatives were of analytical grade, obtained either from Fluka or B.D.H. Fresh solutions of these were prepared in glass-distilled water just prior to the commencement of any experiment.

Copper and uranium metal ions were used in the form of their perchlorates to avoid the possibility of complex formation with anions. The perchlorates were prepared³ from the corresponding nitrates (AnalaR). The concentration of metal ions was estimated by the standard procedures^{4,5}. The details of the other chemicals and measurements of pH were the same as outlined in our earlier papers^{6,7}.

Results and Discussion

The pK and $\log K$ values of substituted succinic and malonic acids were calculated by the method of Irving and Rossotti^{8,9} and are presented in Tables 1-3 together with some literature values. The pK values of CMTSA were also confirmed by the procedure of Block and McIntyre¹⁰.

Effect of substitution of pK values: The molecule of CMTSA is represented as

In an aqueous medium COOH (b) will be involved in inter-molecular hydrogen bonding with its neighbouring molecule to form a dimer. The COOH (a) or COOH (c) would not possibly be involved in such type of bonding because these two could form intra-molecular hydrogen bond. Due to the electron withdrawing effect of thio

[†] Presented at the 68th Session of Indian Science Congress Association at B.H.U., Varanasi, 1981.

* Department of Chemistry, Deogiri College, Aurangabad-431 001.

ARBAD : COPPER AND URANYL CHELATES OF SUBSTITUTED SUCCINIC AND MALONIC ACIDS ETC.

TABLE 1—THERMODYNAMIC DISSOCIATION CONSTANTS OF SUBSTITUTED SUCCINIC AND MALONIC ACIDS IN DIOXANE-WATER MIXTURES

Temp. = 30 ± 0.1°, μ = 0.1 M (NaClO₄)

Ligand/acids	pK ₁ /pK ₂	Dioxane % (v/v)				
		0*	20	40	60	80
Succinic	pK ₁	3.86 (3.86 ^c)	4.56	5.24	6.22	8.48
	pK ₂	5.22 (5.22 ^c)	5.97	6.67	7.56	9.77
Chloro-succinic	pK ₁	2.46 ^a	2.97	3.90	5.24	7.30
	pK ₂	4.41 ^a	4.70	5.75	6.56	8.61
Mercapto-succinic	pK ₁	3.14 (3.15 ^d)	3.72	4.60	5.69	7.93
	pK ₂	4.94 (3.94 ^d)	5.31	5.99	6.91	8.85
Dimercapto-succinic	pK ₁	2.56 ^a	3.08	3.98	5.22	7.49
	pK ₂	4.22 ^a	4.65	5.25	6.30	8.49
Amino-succinic	pK ₁	3.71 (3.71 ^b)	4.49	5.26	6.17	—
	pK ₂	9.63 (9.63 ^b)	10.50	11.43	12.50	—
Hydroxy-succinic	pK ₁	3.22 ^a (3.22 ^d)	3.81	4.57	5.47	7.62
	pK ₂	4.78 ^a (4.78 ^d)	5.29	6.06	6.85	8.86
OMTSA	pK ₁	2.91	3.49	4.39	5.35	7.65
	pK ₂	3.91	4.56	5.38	6.21	8.38
Malonic	pK ₁	5.03	5.55	6.30	7.15	9.08
	pK ₂	2.68 ^a (2.66 ^d)	3.10	3.74	4.74	6.69
Methyl-malonic	pK ₁	5.30 ^a (5.32 ^d)	6.08	6.79	8.05	9.87
	pK ₂	2.98 ^a (2.97 ^d)	3.82	4.54	5.23	7.80
Dimethyl-malonic	pK ₁	5.65 ^a (5.46 ^d)	6.76	7.84	9.05	10.25
	pK ₂	3.02 ^a (3.03 ^d)	3.81	4.72	5.50	8.01
	pK ₁	6.03 ^a	6.97	7.94	9.40	10.67
	pK ₂					

Standard deviation of pK values, (0.01 - 0.04).

* Values given in paranthesis, literature values by other workers.

^a B. R. Arbad, D. N. Shelke and D. V. Jahagirdar, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1979, 56, 947. ^b D. N. Shelke and D. V. Jahagirdar, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1979, 41, 1635. ^c E. G. Base and D. V. Jahagirdar, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1975, 37, 985. ^d L. G. Sillen and A. E. Martell, *Chem. Soc. Spec. Publ.*, 1964, 17; 1971, 25.

TABLE 2—FORMATION CONSTANTS OF Cu^{II}-CHELATES OF SUBSTITUTED SUCCINIC AND MALONIC ACIDS IN DIOXANE-WATER MIXTURES

Temp. = 30 ± 0.1°, μ = 0.1 M (NaClO₄)

Ligand/acids		Dioxane % (v/v)				
		0*	20	40	60	80
Succinic	log K ₁	2.58 (2.58 ^a)	3.40	4.25	6.60	10.61
Chloro-succinic	log K ₁	2.20	3.24	4.56	5.24	8.91
Mercapto-succinic	log K ₁	5.60	6.56	8.48	9.72	14.27
	log K ₂	2.90	4.07	4.54	6.01	10.69
Dimercapto-succinic	log K ₁	3.90	5.40	7.13	9.72	14.86
	log K ₂	1.50	2.60	4.05	6.73	10.89
Amino-succinic	log K ₁	8.40 (8.40 ^e)	9.35	10.75	13.30	—
	log K ₂	6.75 (6.78 ^c)	7.90	9.32	11.60	—
Hydroxy-succinic	log K ₁	3.20	4.28	5.48	7.38	11.84
	log K ₂	1.90	3.45	4.30	5.90	9.49
OMTSA	log K ₁	4.90	6.04	8.98	11.95	17.95
Malonic	log K ₁	5.10 (5.10 ^b)	6.07	7.41	9.33	13.34
	log K ₂	3.37 (3.38 ^b)	4.81	5.81	6.68	—
Methyl-malonic	log K ₁	5.13 (5.19 ^d)	5.78	8.48	10.19	14.09
	log K ₂	3.53	4.78	5.90	7.50	11.59
Dimethyl-malonic	log K ₁	4.82 (4.84 ^d)	5.70	6.59	10.10	13.61
	log K ₂	3.48	4.20	5.60	6.60	10.73

Standard deviation of log K values, (0.01 - 0.05).

* Values in parenthesis, literature values.

^a Ref. as in Table 1. ^b D. N. Shelke and D. V. Jahagirdar, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1979, 41, 925. ^c G. Brooks and L. D. Pettit, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1977, 1918. ^d Ref. as in Table 1.

TABLE 3—FORMATION CONSTANTS OF UO₂^{II}-CHELATES OF SUBSTITUTED SUCCINIC AND MALONIC ACIDS IN DIOXANE-WATER MIXTURES

Temp. = 30 ± 0.1°, μ = 0.1 M (NaClO₄)

Ligand/acids		Dioxane % (v/v)				
		0*	20	40	60	80
Succinic	log K ₁	4.48 (4.48 ^e)	5.71	6.89	8.80	13.65
	log K ₂	3.30	4.01	4.85	6.40	10.07
Chloro-succinic	log K ₁	3.57	4.04	6.42	7.86	12.21
	log K ₂	2.95	3.45	4.26	5.15	8.14
Mercapto-succinic	log K ₁	3.70 (3.70 ^e)	4.67	6.05	7.45	11.73
	log K ₂	2.65	3.60	4.38	5.54	8.45
Dimercapto-succinic	log K ₁	3.06 ^a	4.04	6.09	7.72	12.37
	log K ₂	2.40 ^a	3.32	4.02	5.38	9.48
Amino-succinic	log K ₁	8.71 (8.71 ^b)	9.25	10.70	13.10	—
	log K ₂	7.40	7.85	8.44	9.64	—
Hydroxy-succinic	log K ₁	5.50 ^a	6.67	8.26	10.20	14.54
	log K ₂	3.63 ^a	4.60	6.10	8.20	12.99
OMTSA	log K ₁	4.65	6.20	8.50	11.50	17.97
	log K ₂	3.41	3.57	4.25	5.17	7.60
Malonic	log K ₁	5.56 (5.56 ^d)	5.93	7.41	8.35	14.16
	log K ₂	3.80 (3.80 ^d)	4.43	5.50	7.07	11.24
Methyl-malonic	log K ₁	6.70 ^a	8.06	9.95	11.40	15.76
	log K ₂	4.22 ^a	5.84	6.73	8.20	12.98
Dimethyl-malonic	log K ₁	6.32 ^a	7.28	9.40	11.10	15.40
	log K ₂	4.05 ^a	5.20	6.60	8.00	12.19

Standard deviation of log K values, (0.01 - 0.05).

* Values in parenthesis indicate literature values by other workers.

^a Ref. as in Table 1. ^b D. N. Shelke and D. V. Jahagirdar, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1978, 16, 60. ^c S. Ramamoorthy and M. Santappa, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1971, 33, 1775. ^d D. N. Shelke and D. V. Jahagirdar, *Curr. Sci.*, 1976, 45, 163. ^e S. Ramamoorthy and M. Santappa, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1968, 41, 1330; 1969, 42, 411.

group, COOH (c) carbon would be more positive than the carbon atom of COOH (a). Under these conditions, intra-molecular hydrogen bonding would utilise the hydrogen from the COOH (c). This means, the hydrogen of the COOH (a) is unaffected by hydrogen bonding, and suggests that the hydrogen from the COOH (a) would dissociate first and the value of 2.91 should be assigned to it. The second hydrogen might be expected to come from the COOH (b) because inter-molecular hydrogen bonding is generally weaker than intra-molecular bonding. The COOH (c) group would, therefore, be the last one to dissociate. As regards the remaining ligands, the probability of dissociation of any of the COOH groups is equal for succinic and dimercaptosuccinic acid. In chloro-, mercapto-, and hydroxy-succinic acids, because of the electron withdrawing influence of the substituted groups, it is expected that a COOH group attached to the carbon atom carrying these substituents would dissociate first than the other carbon atom. The dissociation tendency of aspartic acid is very well known.

Effect of dielectric constant on pK and log K values: In the present case the variation in pK values of the carboxylic acids is compared with succinic acid which is considered as a parent acid. All the plots of the first dissociation constants (pK₁) gave straight lines of unit slope with correlation

coefficient between 0.96 and 1.0. The plots for pK_2 were also linear and with slope values 0.6. It can, therefore, be concluded that the effect of solvent medium is almost identical for all the carboxylic acids¹¹.

In the systems studied, the values of $pK/\log K$ increase with the decrease in dielectric constant of the medium. The values of $(\log K_1 - \log K_2)$ have been calculated for Cu^{II} and UO_2^{II} complexes of substituted succinic and malonic acids in dioxane-water mixtures. It is seen from these values that difference between $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ continuously increases with the increase in dioxane percentage. This means that either $\log K_1$ is relatively increasing, or $\log K_2$ is relatively decreasing as the dielectric constant is decreased. The lowering of dielectric constant would increase the electrostatic force of attraction between the metal ion and the negatively charged or neutral ligand to form more stable 1:1 complex. The formation of 1:2 complex is of the same type. The plots of $pK/\log K$ vs $1/D$ were non-linear, while those against mole fraction of dioxane exhibit linearity. In the plots of pK vs $1/D$ the first three points invariably fell on a straight line.

Validity of $\log K = apK + b$, relation: The linear relationship between $\log K$ and pK has been found to hold for a series of closely related ligands by many workers¹²⁻¹⁵. The plots of $\log K_1$ vs $pK_1 + pK_2$ were linear, though the points corresponding to mercapto compounds fell off the line passing through the five substituted-succinic acids. The slope values were very close to 1.0, hence it

can be concluded that there is no extra π -bonding in metal complexation.

Acknowledgement

The author wishes to record his sincere thanks to Dr. D. V. Jahagirdar, Reader in Chemistry, Marathwada University, for his valuable suggestions and continuous encouragement.

References

1. G. E. CHENEY, Q. FERNADO and H. FREISER, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, **63**, 2055.
2. A. ARGEN and G. SCHWARZENBACH, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1955, **38**, 1920.
3. K. B. JABALPURWALA, K. A. VENKATACHALAM and M. B. KABADI, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1964, **26**, 1027.
4. G. SCHWARZENBACH, "Complexometric Titrations", Methuen, London, 1957, pp. 69-82.
5. A. I. VOGEL, "A Textbook of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", Longmans Green, London, 1975, p. 589.
6. D. V. JAHAGIRDAR, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1977, **15**, 752.
7. D. V. JAHAGIRDAR and D. D. KHANOLKAR, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1973, **35**, 921.
8. H. IRVING and H. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 3997.
9. H. IRVING and H. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 2904.
10. R. P. BLOCK and G. H. MCINTYRE, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **75**, 5667.
11. Y. KONDO, T. MATSUI and N. TAKURA, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1969, **42**, 1037.
12. J. G. JONES, J. C. TOMKINSON, J. B. POOLE and R. J. P. WILLIAMS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 2001.
13. D. D. PERRIN, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 3125.
14. M. CALVIN and K. WILSON, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, **67**, 2003.
15. Z. L. ERNST and J. MENASHI, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1963, **59**, 2838.